
Academic Achievement of Student–Teachers in English in Relation To Their Attitude, Achievement Motivation and Perceptual Factors

Ashok Mittimani

Assistant Professor S.J.V.P. College of Education Hirekalmath, Honnali,
Dist. Davanagere

I. Introduction

English occupies an important place in the world today. Every country, every citizen of the world prefers to learn English. English has become the channel of communication in all sorts of communication gadgets operating with English. Much of the communication at the administrative level and organizational level is being done in English with little emphasis on regional or local language. English is influencing the overall language development of learners. The effect of mother tongue or local native language, which the student is learning at initial stages, is influencing the learning of English language skills in articulation, reading, writing and pronunciation. So the method adopted by the teachers is crucial in teaching better English languages skills to the youngsters. Thus, in the study an effort has been made to study the academic achievement of student-teachers in methodology of teaching English in relation to their attitude towards the subject English, achievement motivation and perceptions of student-teachers of learning English and it's language skills ; and teaching English and it's teaching skills.

II. Achievement Motivation

Importance giving to academic performance at all educational levels has considerably increased during the recent years. The concept of achievement motivation has generated a major current of activity in the psychology of motivation. It has been an object of considerable research and discussion in the recent years. Achievement is influenced by many personality factors. Among these factors “achievement motivation” is the factor, which seems to be the most important factor. Reports of these studies achievement motivation has been found to be significantly and positively related to academic achievement (Sinha, 1967 ; Srivastave, 1974 ; Christian, 1977 ; Contractor, 1977 ; Prabha Mehta, 1990 ; Gupta, 1993).

It has also been found that achievement motivation has no influence on academic achievement under certain conditions (Walayatiram, 1974 ; Seshadre, 1980; Sundrarajan and Selvaraj Gnanaguru, 1992). Thus, the opinion seems to be divided on this issue, it is therefore, decided to study the achievement performance in relation to their academic achievement motivation. Hence, the study is timely and also important from the point of view of the selection of the students on a particular class and their performance in academic stream.

Attitude

The term attitude is defined by freeman as “a dispositional readiness to respond to certain situations, persons, objects or ideas in a consistent manner, which has been learned and has become one's typical' mode of response”.

Chave (1928) an attitude is a complex of feelings, desires, fears, convictions, prejudices or other tendencies that have given a set of readiness to act to a person because of varied experiences.

Thurstone (1931) attitude is the affect for or against a psychological object. The term psychological object may refer to a physical object, a person, an idea, a plan of action, a form of conduct... In fact, it may refer to any idea about which the subject may express positive or negative effect.

It is a tendency to react in a certain way towards a designated class of stimuli. These are the ways in which an individual things, feels and acts. Attitude always arouses one's feelings and emotions. Attitude ranges from Positive extreme to Negative extreme. Attitudes vary in the amount of favourable or unfavourable. *Favourable Attitude* implies positive tendency towards the English. However, *Unfavourable attitude* is the negative tendency towards the English.

Perception

Perception refers to the way the world looks, sounds, feels, tastes or smells. In other words perception can be defined as whatever is experienced by a person. Human beings live in a world of stimuli. Stimuli activate receptors, which in turn send messages to the brain, which eventually uses this information to guide behaviour. While interacting with environment, the organism is impinged by a number of stimuli. Stimuli are received by sensation. Sensation is a raw material of experience. When meaning is added to the sensation, by the help of past experience and learning it becomes perception. For instance, seeing a bird like object flying in the sky is a sensation. When it is clearly observed and attended to and saying it an aeroplane is perception. Perception has become the meeting ground of experimental, clinical and social psychology. It is an integrated complex process involving sensation, attention and meaning.

III. Review: An Overview

The investigator has reviewed the research studies conducted so far. Among them few are Indian studies and few are conducted in abroad studies. These reveals that the English language proficiency of student-teachers, perception of primary education trainees, about teaching, school teachers perception about teaching and learning, creative writing skills in English among college students, students' perception of their teachers' attitude, learning communicative skills in English, perception of student-teacher about teaching of science, and teacher's perception on the learning difficulties and development of English language skills. Then few studies laid their focus on perception of middle schoolers about school disciplinary practices, perception of the skills, perception of motivating factors impacting the academic achievement, effect of family involvement training for English language learners, teachers attitude towards English language learners, perceived barriers to English language learning, first grade teachers' perceptions of and expectations for ELL students, teachers' perception of mathematics and science training, teacher perception of academic achievement, student perception of biology content, teachers' perception of play therapy skills development, etc. Most of them used random sampling techniques for choosing the sample. Both the standardized and self-constructed tools were used for conducting the studies.

IV. Statement of the Problem

Thus, the study is entitled as "*Academic Achievement of Student-Teachers in English in Relation to their Attitude, Achievement Motivation and Perceptual Factors*".

Variables

Independent Variable

- i. Perceptual Factors associated with teaching and learning English
- ii. Attitude towards English
- iii. Achievement Motivation in learning and teaching English

Dependent Variable

- i. Academic Achievement in teaching English Methodology

V. Objectives of the Study

The researcher has formulated the following objectives for the present study :

1. To study the relationship between the Attitude towards English and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
2. To study the relationship between the Achievement Motivation and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
3. To study the relationship between the perception of student-teachers about learning English and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
4. To study the relationship between the perception of student-teachers about teaching English and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
5. To study the relationship between the perception of student-teachers about learning listening skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
6. To study the relationship between the perception of student-teachers about teaching listening skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
7. To study the relationship between the perception of student-teachers about learning speaking skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
8. To study the relationship between the perception of student-teachers about teaching speaking skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
9. To study the relationship between the perception of student-teachers about learning reading skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
10. To study the relationship between the perception of student-teachers about teaching reading skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
11. To study the relationship between the perception of student-teachers about learning writing skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
12. To study the relationship between the perception of student-teachers about teaching writing skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.

VI. Research Hypotheses

The researcher has formulated the following hypotheses for the present study.

1. There is a significant relationship between the Attitude towards English and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
2. There is a significant relationship between the Achievement Motivation and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
3. There is a significant relationship between the perception of student-teachers about learning English and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
4. There is a significant relationship between the perception of student-teachers about teaching English and academic achievement of student-teachers in English..
5. There is a significant relationship between the perception of student-teachers about learning listening skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
6. There is a significant relationship between the perception of student-teachers about teaching listening skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
7. There is a significant relationship between the perception of student-teachers about learning speaking skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
8. There is a significant relationship between the perception of student-teachers about teaching speaking skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
9. There is a significant relationship between the perception of student-teachers about learning reading skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
10. There is a significant relationship between the perception of student-teachers about teaching reading skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English..
11. There is a significant relationship between the perception of student-teachers about learning writing skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.
12. There is a significant relationship between the perception of student-teachers about teaching writing skills and academic achievement of student-teachers in English.

VII. Definition of Technical Terms

Achievement Motivation

The term motivation refers to any organismic state that mobilizes activity which is in some sense selective and directing. In the present study, achievement motivation which is characterized by a desire to attain a high standard of excellence and accomplish a unique objective. Achievement motivation is a disposition to strive for success in situation where an individual's performance is evaluated.

Perception

It refers to the personal meanings that govern behaviour. The term 'perception' and 'perceptual factor' are used to convey the same idea.

Student-Teachers

By this the investigator means the graduates and post-graduates undergoing B.Ed. degree course in Colleges of Education affiliated to Davanagere University during the academic year 2018-2020.

VIII. Research Method

The descriptive method has been used in the present study. A descriptive study describes and interprets what *is*. It is concerned with considerations or relationships that exist opinions that are held, processes that are going on, effects that are evident, or trends that are developing. It is primarily concerned with the present, although it often considers past events and influences as they relate to current conditions.

The method adapted in the present study is a descriptive research, which is particularly appropriate in the behavioural sciences because many of the types of behaviour that interest the researcher cannot be arranged in a realistic setting.

Tools Used

In order to assess the students teachers perception of English Teaching and Learning scale developed and validated by Samuel Koilpillai (2006) was adopted. For assessing student-teachers' scale of perception of teaching learning of language skills in English developed and validated by Samuel Koilpillai (2006) was adopted. Achievement motivation scale developed by Robinson (1970) was adopted. Attitude towards English developed and validated by P. S. Chandrakumar (2006) was adopted.

Sample

The sample for the study was consisted of student-teachers studying in colleges of education in the jurisdiction of Davanagere University. From the total population of 857 student-teachers, around 510 student-teachers were selected using random sampling technique for the present study. The selected sample is considered as representative of the entire population of the study.

Collection of Data

The investigator has personally visited Colleges of Education under the jurisdiction of Davanagere University. The student-teachers were given necessary instructions about the various tools, and motivated them to respond genuinely to all the items. Further, the tools like personal data sheet and the selected scales were administered. The data was collected as per the required norms and used for further analysis. In the current research, Academic Achievement in English of respective sample was collected from the result sheets of the university examinations held during May / June 2019.

Statistical Technique

The investigator was used the Pearson's Production Moment Correlation technique in order to find out the relationship independent and dependent variables involved in the study.

IX. Analysis of the Data

Table – 1: Correlations of Academic Achievement of Student-Teachers with Attitude towards English, Achievement Motivation and Perception Factors

Independent Variables	Correlation Coefficients- Academic Achievement			
	"r"	"t"	P-value	Significance
Attitude towards English	0.8988	46.2238	< 0.05	Yes
Achievement Motivation	0.7478	25.3826	< 0.05	Yes
Perception of Learning of English language	0.8287	33.3683	< 0.05	Yes
Perception of Teaching English	0.7356	24.4749	< 0.05	Yes
Perception of Learning Listening Skills	0.8127	31.4314	< 0.05	Yes
Perception of Teaching Listening Skills	0.7126	22.8910	< 0.05	Yes
Perception of Learning Speaking Skills	0.7841	28.4767	< 0.05	Yes
Perception of Teaching Speaking Skills	0.6991	22.0346	< 0.05	Yes
Perception of Learning Reading Skills	0.6339	18.4729	< 0.05	Yes
Perception of Teaching Reading Skills	0.7342	24.3724	< 0.05	Yes
Perception of Learning Writing Skills	0.7216	23.4934	< 0.05	Yes
Perception of Teaching Writing Skills	0.8312	33.7018	< 0.05	Yes

Findings

The analysis of the above table reveals the following findings :

Hypothesis – 1

The obtained 't' value 46.2238 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Attitude towards English of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 2

The obtained 't' value 25.3826 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and *Achievement Motivation* of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 3

The obtained 't' value 33.3683 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Perceptual Factor – *Perception of Learning English language* of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 4

The obtained 't' value 24.4749 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Perceptual Factor – *Perception of Teaching English language* of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 5

The obtained 't' value 31.4314 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Perceptual Factor – *Perception of Learning Listening Skills* of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 6

The obtained 't' value 22.8910 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Perceptual Factor – *Perception of Teaching Listening Skills* of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 7

The obtained 't' value 28.4767 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Perceptual Factor – *Perception of Learning Speaking Skills* of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 8

The obtained 't' value 22.0346 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Perceptual Factor – *Perception of Teaching Speaking Skills* of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 9

The obtained 't' value 18.4729 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Perceptual Factor – *Perception of Learning Reading Skills* of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 10

The obtained 't' value 24.3724 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Perceptual Factor – *Perception of Teaching Reading Skills* of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 11

The obtained 't' value 23.4934 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Perceptual Factor – *Perception of Learning Writing Skills* of student-teachers is accepted.

Hypothesis – 12

The obtained 't' value 33.7018 is greater than the tabled 't' value 1.96 at 0.05 level. It is, therefore, concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between two groups in respect of the variables under consideration. It thus implies that the obtained correlation is significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is a positive and significant relationship between the Academic Achievement and Perceptual Factor – *Perception of Teaching Writing Skills* of student-teachers is accepted.

X. Conclusion

From the above analysis, it is conducted that the Attitude towards English, Achievement Motivation, and Perceptual Factors – *Perception of Learning of English Language, Perception of Teaching English Language, Perception of Learning Listening Skills, Perception of Teaching Listening Skill, Perception of Learning Speaking Skills, Perception of Teaching Speaking Skills, Perception of Learning Reading Skills, Perception of Teaching Reading Skills, Perception of Learning Writing Skills and Perception of Teaching Writing Skills* are having positive and significant relationship with the Academic Achievement of student-teachers in English. Thus, it is implied that the selected factors will facilitate the Academic Achievement of student-teachers in English language.

XI. Discussion

The attitude towards English, achievement motivation and perception of student-teachers are related to academic achievement in English. It upholds the assumption of the investigator regarding the selected variables regarding the teaching and learning of English are promoting the achievement of student-teachers in English. The prevalent condition of teaching and learning English in the State of Karnataka may be in no way different from what is being found among the student-teachers in other Colleges of Education.

The study was undertaken on the hypotheses that understanding the perception of student-teachers in Colleges of Education about learning and teaching English won't be different from what the people in Karnataka might perceive teaching and learning of English. In fact, the student-teachers in Colleges of Education would reflect what the general population in Karnataka would perceive about school education in general and English languages teaching and learning in particular. Therefore, the investigator infers that the present nature of perception about teaching and learning of English would be just the reflection of the status of English language teaching from the point of view of the teachers and the parents.

XII. Educational Implications

The implications of the results of the study may be stated as follows :

The student-teachers who are joining the teacher education programme with major subjects in pure science or arts or language other than English may be given series of orientation to take effort to communicate in English in all circumstances. Series of workshops may be organized to provide practical experience in listening speaking, reading and writing well before the commencement of practical teaching. Integrated spoken English programme may be introduced along with other subjects so as to provide continuity in the development of the speaking skill.

The teacher educators may be encouraged to make use of English for curriculum transaction as much as possible, though vernacular is permissible or even adopted as the medium of instruction. All activities intended for developing teaching competence, leadership qualities, social characteristics and administrative abilities may be executed by the good use of English. The institution may organize face-to-face programmes with outside experts in the field of English to enable the student-teachers to understand the liberal use of English in different circumstances. The institution may provide full-fledged courses on spoken English, creative writing, understanding grammatical correctness, literary criticism, etc., to student-teachers who may opt for them. The daily schedule may be planned in such a way that individual student-teachers by turn would be able to face the students as well as the staff at least once and share his or her thoughts and experiences for a few minutes preferably in English.

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